

Biodistribution of iron and zinc in peanuts: Analysis of biomolecular fractions

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Abstract: Peanuts are good source of plant proteins for human beings. Peanuts are also rich in iron and zinc. Iron is one of the essential macro elements for human body, whereas zinc is an essential micro element for brain development and enzymatic actions. In this work peanut proteins have been extracted and purified. A brief study has also been done on total iron and zinc content of peanut using atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). Different protein fractions of peanut have been analyzed for their iron and zinc content and compared with total protein bound metal species. The concentrations of the free metals have been studied as well. Results indicated that peanuts are rich sources of these essential elements and have a distribution in various molecular fractions of it. These results may be useful to researches concerned with the food industry where various food components are processed to meet different dietary requirements.

Keywords: Arachin, conarachin I, conarachin II, iron, zinc, peanut, AAS.

Introduction

Peanut is one of the most important sources of plant proteins. The oil free peanut meal contains nearly 50–60% protein of good nutritional quality. Not only proteins, peanut is a good resource of amino acid, arginine which has an important role in converting blood sugar into energy. Arginine present in peanut helps to improve blood flow, relax our arteries and lowers blood pressure¹. Another bioactive compound present in peanut is resveratrol that prevents cardiovascular disease, cancer and inflammation. Peanut is a good source of essential macro and microelements such as iron, zinc, etc.². Research shows high content of iron, zinc, magnesium etc. in peanut. Peanut grows at the root of the plant where it is in contact with the soil. That's why they are also called ground nuts and contain a high quantity of minerals coming directly from the soil.

Peanut proteins mainly consist of arachin, conarachin I and conarachin II. They are globulin proteins (saline soluble). These proteins contain a

large portion of aromatic amino acids, tyrosine, phenylalanine, and tryptophan. These arachin and conarachins have components Ara h 1 and Ara h 3 which are found to be allergenic to certain individuals. This allergen can suddenly produce syndrome like anaphylaxis which may trigger life threatening situation. Proteins have tendency to show specific affinity towards specific metal ions; some are important to maintain their native structure and some for their function. Proteins can bind metal ions through main chain amino and carboxyl groups^{3,4}. Metal ions can also be attached with specific sites of amino acid side chains, such as carboxylate moiety of glutamine acid and aspartic acid, ring nitrogen of histidine, tryptophan etc., can bind with Ca²⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Fe²⁺. Easily polarizable or soft metals can form covalent bonds with proteins whereas low polarizable or hard metals show electrostatic interaction⁵. Certain metal ions have important biological activities. Zinc is essential for growth and development in living organisms. Biological func-

tions of zinc include building up immunity, help in DNA metabolism and repair, assist in normal reproduction, vision, taste, and cognition⁶⁻⁸. Zinc is also essential for neuronal growth, and neurotransmission⁹. Iron is a necessary trace element found in nearly all living organisms. Iron plays an important role in biology, forming complexes with molecular oxygen in hemoglobin and myoglobin. Iron is also the metal used at the active site of many important redox enzymes dealing with cellular respiration and oxidation and reduction in plants and animals. Iron-containing enzymes and proteins, often containing heme prosthetic groups, they participate in many biological oxidations and in transport¹⁰.

A considerable fraction of Fe and Zn in the trace elemental composition has been studied in various nut and seed samples by earlier researchers¹¹⁻¹⁴. Peanut is a potential seed candidate to concentrate these trace elements in different forms as it directly remains attached to the ground. The aim of this work is to find out the iron and zinc content in different biomolecular fractions of peanut as well as in peanut as a whole. Keeping in mind that peanut is a popular item for the food processing industries where peanut butter, peanut protein extract, etc., are regularly processed, an idea of trace element distribution in its various biomolecular fractions will be useful in nutritional point of view. In this work proteins present in peanut were separated, purified and their concentrations were estimated by Bradford method¹⁵. Elements like iron and zinc have been estimated using atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS), not only their overall concentration but their occurrence in different biomolecular parts of peanut and concentrations in each portions have been isolated and studied. The protein bound portions of Fe and Zn have been analyzed which may be available after protein metabolism. The results may have useful applications to the food industry where various food components are processed to meet different requirements.

Results and discussion

The concentration of purified protein fractions, arachin, conarachin I and conarachin II were estimated from the Bradford assay and were found to be

as follows: Arachin: 0.0176 mg/mL; Conarachin I: 0.0135 mg/mL; Conarachin II: 0.0166 mg/mL.

The separated portions of pure arachin, conarachin have characteristic peaks in their UV-Visible spectrum which are shown in Fig. 4. Arachin shows a λ_{max} at 275 nm, conarachin I at 265 nm and conarachin II at 278 nm which are quite closely spaced as all of them are proteins but still have distinct characteristics. The results of gel electrophoresis indicate that the high molecular weight fraction (72.4 kD) of both arachin and conarachin II were obtained by this method (Fig. 5). The estimations of Fe and Zn in different fractions of peanut were done using a suitable standard curve using AAS.

The estimation of total iron and zinc content in peanut was found to be 146 ± 10 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 136 ± 3 $\mu\text{g/g}$ respectively. A differential estimation of different biomolecular fractions of peanut for their iron and zinc content reveals that the fat portion is devoid of these two metal ions. The concentration of arachin bound Fe and Zn were found to be 8.88 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 0.78 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ respectively. The conarachin I bound Fe was 11.27 ± 0.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and that of Zn was 2.6 ± 0.26 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The conarachin II bound Fe was 17.26 ± 0.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and that of Zn was 1.48 ± 0.26 $\mu\text{g/g}$. The protein unbound concentrations for Fe and Zn were 31.66 ± 1.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and 71.45 ± 1.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ respectively. The carbohydrate matrix contains 46.49 ± 1.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Fe and 9.38 ± 0.51 $\mu\text{g/g}$ Zn. The lipid part was found to be devoid of Fe and Zn (Fig. 6).

Only 6% of the total iron remains bound with the arachin part, 7.7% with the conarachin I part, 11.8% with conarachin II and 21.68% remains in the protein unbound supernatant (i.e., as free metal ions). The rest of the iron probably resides either in the carbohydrate or in the fibrous part of peanut. However, the majority portion of Zn (52.5%) remains in the protein unbound part. The arachin part contains only 0.57%, conarachin I part contains 1.9% and conarachin II part contains 1.08% of the total Zn. All the protein bound and protein unbound Fe and Zn may be available for metabolism after the proteolysis of peanut protein.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents:

For AAS, Thermo Fischer Scientific (Model: ice 3300, Thermo Electron Manufacturing Ltd., Cambridge, UK) was used. Hollow cathode lamp (Cathodeon, Cambridge, UK) 15 mA for Fe and 10 mA for Zn were used. The UV-Visible spectra were obtained using an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer (GMI, Ramsey, Minnesota, USA). A digital pH meter Systronics, Kolkata, India (Type no. 335) was used to measure and adjust the pH of different solutions. Centrifugation was done using Hermle (Labortechnik GmbH, Wehingen, Germany) microprocessor controlled universal refrigerated high speed table top centrifuge (Model: Z 36 K). Microwave digester (ETHOS 1600, New York) was used to digest the peanut samples using HPLC grade HNO_3 . Petroleum ether, ammonium sulfate, phosphate buffer, were obtained from MERCK (Darmstadt, Germany). Fe and Zn standard solutions of Sigma-Aldrich (Dorset, UK) were used for calibration in AAS.

Peanuts were procured from local market and dried in the sun. The brown skin was taken off and blanched using mortar pestle. The solid mass was then refluxed with petroleum ether for 2 h. The lipid part was thus extracted out. This fat free mass of peanut was then filtered out and the air dried residue was taken as peanut flour for further processing. 0.1% NaOH solution (w/v) was added and stirred well to the flour so as to extract sodium proteinate in aqueous medium. Dilute H_2SO_4 was then added dropwise with constant stirring till the pH of solution came down to 5. The protein precipitated out at this isoelectric pH. White precipitate was allowed to settle and was centrifuged. The residue was washed to make it free from salts. Peanut proteins are mainly globulins (soluble in saline water). So to the residue 2% NaCl (w/v) solution was added to dissolve out conarachin I and II in 2% NaCl solution. Then it was further centrifuged and the supernatant was preserved in refrigerator. The process is schematically presented in Fig. 1.

Separation of conarachin I and conarachin II:

The 2% NaCl solution containing conarachin part

Fig. 1. Extraction scheme of total protein.

was saturated to 32% with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solution and kept at 4°C for at least 4 h. This solution was centrifuged at $4000 \times g$ for 20 min and the supernatant was further saturated to 42% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and centrifuged further. The supernatant was dialyzed against 0.01 (M) phosphate buffer of pH 7.9 in 0.5 M NaCl solu-

Fig. 2. Separation scheme of conarachin I and conarachin II.

tion (extraction buffer (EB)) to remove SO_4^{2-} ions. Schematic representation of this extraction and purification process is shown in Fig. 2.

Pure conarachin solution was fractionated into conarachin I and conarachin II using Superose-6 gel chromatography column using EB. 2 mL samples were continuously collected in eppendorf tubes after pooling out the void volume. Absorption spectrum was studied for each of the 2 mL samples to determine the concentration of the protein. Fractions immediately after void volume containing high molecular weight fraction conarachin II were pooled first followed by those of conarachin I. The protein solutions were concentrated using concentrating columns (Pall Corporation Macrosep Advance Centrifugal Device) to remove the buffer. Concentration of the resulting protein solutions were measured using the Bradford method¹⁵.

Separation of arachin:

The defatted peanut meal was homogenized with 0.01 M phosphate buffer (saline) and stirred for 1 h. The solution was centrifuged for 30 min maintaining the temperature at 27°C and at a speed of 3500*g. (NH₄)₂SO₄ was added to the clear supernatant to make it to 18% saturation and kept at 4°C for 2 h and then centrifuged for 30 min again. The pellet was then dissolved in EB, saturated to 9% with (NH₄)₂SO₄ and kept at 4°C for 1 h. Then the solution was centrifuged again and the pellet was redissolved in EB and dialysed against EB to remove the excess salt (Fig. 3). The concentration of the proteins was measured by using Bradford method¹⁵.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis:

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis was carried out using 15% acrylamide gel in 8.5×0.6 cm gel tubes. Protein samples (1–5 µg) were loaded on the gel. Electrophoresis was performed in 0.02 M tris buffer in glycine, pH 8.3, at a constant voltage of 80 V for stacking and 100 V for redissolving for total 3 h. The gels were stained with 0.1% brilliant blue R-250 and destained by diffusion in methanol-acetic acid medium. A standard “Page ruler unstained broad range protein ladder” from Fermentas was used as molecular weight marker.

Fig. 3. Extraction scheme of arachin.

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectrum of arachin and conarachin I and conarachin II.

Estimation of iron and zinc in different fractions of peanut:

The different samples that were analyzed for their Fe and Zn content are as follows:

- (i) Crude peanut: Obtained directly from market.

Fig. 5. SDS-PAGE pattern of peanut protein fractions: Lane I: conarachin I; Lane II: arachin; Lane III: conarachin II; Lane IV: Scale.

(ii) Defatted peanut meal: The residue obtained after reflux in PET ether.

(iii) Lipid portion: PET ether extract.

(iv) Protein part; (a) Conarachin I, (b) Conarachin II, (c) Arachin.

(v) Protein unbound part: The supernatant after precipitation of total protein at pH 5.

(vi) Carbohydrate matrix: The solid left after treatment with 0.1% NaOH solution.

All the above samples were microwave digested in HNO₃ (HPLC grade) for 15 min each and subjected to AAS analysis for Fe and Zn.

Preparation of standard calibration curves for Fe and Zn:

Standard stock solutions of Fe and Zn (1000 ppm each) were diluted quantitatively to 1 and 2 ppm solutions to obtain the standard calibration curves.

Fig. 6. Distribution of iron and zinc in peanut.

Microwave digested solutions (1 to 6) were treated as unknown solutions and analyzed for their Fe and Zn content.

Conclusion

Peanuts are therefore large source of essential elements, Fe and Zn which may remain associated with its different biomolecular fractions. These elements may be made available to the body at different stages of metabolism after digestion at different sites of the digestive system. The results are significant as trace concentration of Fe and Zn associated in the food components is a matter of prime concern for several food industries while processing. Even for designing food supplements, only supplements made from 100% food is considered for supporting optimal health. It is also strongly evidenced that the bioavailability and/or effectiveness of mineral containing foods is greater than that of isolated inorganic mineral salts or mineral chelates¹⁶⁻²⁰. This is the prime motivation of this research report.

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